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Design of an indoor Li-Fi system for small office

Dr.Hanaa Omer Aboalogasim Omer

Abstract

This paper provides an effect of four LEDs emission and calculate the optical power distribution of LOS link at receiving plane for indoor li-fi system with signal to noise ratio and other performance parameters. In this research simulation programs MATLAB is used to configure and design of an indoor Li-Fi system with optimal optical power distribution of LOS Link at receiving Plane for the typical office which area size $8 \times 8 \times 3.5m^3$.

The goals of this paper are to make the power distribution uniform with no dead zone area and less fluctuation in the illumination plus find the maximum achievable data rate in diffuse channel and the results have achieved goals.

Keywords: Visible light communication, VLC, light fidelity LiFi , Light-emitting diodes LED.

1. Introduction

LiFi is a wireless communication technology that uses the infrared and visible light spectrum for high speed data communication. LiFi, first coined in [1] extends the concept of visible light communication (VLC) to achieve high speed, secure, bi-directional and fully networked wireless communications [2,10]. It is important to note that LiFi supports user mobility and multiuser access .The size of the infrared and visible light spectrum together is approximately 2600 times the size of the entire radio frequency spectrum of 300GHz [3]. LiFi could be classified as nm wave communication. LiFi uses light emitting diodes (LEDs) for high speed

wireless communication, and speeds of over 3Gb/s from a single micro-light emitting diode (LED) [4] have been demonstrated using optimized direct current optical orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (DCO-OFDM) modulation [5]. Given that there is a widespread deployment of LED lighting in homes, offices and streetlights because of the energy-efficiency of LEDs, there is an added benefit for LiFi cellular deployment in that it can build on existing lighting infrastructures. Moreover, the cell sizes can be reduced further compared with mm-wave communication leading to the concept of LiFi attocells [6].

Figure (1) VLC network.

1.2 Li-Fi networking

Figure(2) illustrates the concept of a Li-Fi attocell network. The room is lit by several light fixtures, which provide illumination. Each light is driven by a Li-Fi modem or a Li-Fi chip and, therefore, also serves as an

optical base station or access point (AP). The optical base stations are connected to the core network by high speed backhaul connections. The light fixtures also have an integrated infrared detector to receive signals from the terminals. The illuminating lights are modulated at high rates. The resulting high frequency flickers which are much higher than the refresh rate of a computer monitor are not visible to the occupants of the room. Power and data can be provided to each light fixture using a number of different techniques, including power-line communication (PLC) [7,8].

Figure(2) LiFi attocells

2. System Model

2.1 Location and Positioning algorithms

Investigations within this field demonstrate that positioning algorithms proposed so far can be categorized into three types: triangulation, scene analysis, and proximity, in this paper we used Triangulation.

2.1.1 Triangulation

Triangulation is the general name for positioning algorithms which use the geometric properties of triangles for location estimation. Triangulation has two branches: trilateration and angulations [12]. In trilateration methods, the target location is estimated by measuring its distances from multiple reference points. For all the VLC-based indoor positioning systems proposed, the reference points are light sources and the target is an optical receiver. The distances are almost impossible to measure directly; however, they can be mathematically calculated from other measurements such as received signal strength (RSS), time-of-arrival (TOA) or time-difference-of-arrival (TDOA). On the other hand, angulations measures angles relative to several reference points (angle-of-arrival (AOA)), after which location estimation is carried out by finding intersection points of direction lines which are radii from reference points [10].

Triangulation – angulations

In AOA-based systems, the receiver measures angles of arriving signals from several reference points. The target's location is then determined as the intersection of direction lines (figure (3)). Typically two light sources are needed to realize 2-D and three for 3-D positioning. Interestingly, we can find a historical trace back to older photogrammetric techniques [13] with many similarities. The greatest advantage of AOA-based systems is that no time synchronization is needed. Another advantage is that it is relatively easier to detect the AOA of the incoming signals in the optical domain with an imaging receiver, compared to employing complex antenna arrays used in radio-wave approaches. The widely deployed front-facing cameras, which are inherently imaging receivers, on smart phones and tablets have brought opportunities for this method to become

practicable on mobile consumer electronics. However, to achieve a good performance for a real system, the lighting infrastructure may have to be adjusted since most of these cameras have a very limited field-of-view (FOV). More generally, the positioning accuracy of an AOA based system will downgrade when the target gets farther from the light sources due to the limited spatial resolution of the imaging receivers. A positioning accuracy of 5 cm is reported when using an imaging receiver with a resolution of 1296×964 pixels [14]. In [15,16], researchers proposed a two phase positioning algorithm which makes use of multipath effects due to reflections into consideration. Computer simulations showed that a median accuracy of 13.95 cm can be achieved.

Figure(3) Positioning using angulations.

To obtain the least square solution for an AOA-based system, suppose α_i denotes the measured angle-of-arrival with respect to the i th transmitter, which is given by:

$$\tan^{-1} \alpha_i = \frac{y - Y_i}{x - X_i} \quad \text{Equation (1)}$$

where $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, x and y target axis position .[9]

2.2 Optical Power Distribution of LOS Link

$$P_r = P_t \cdot \frac{(m_i + 1)}{2\pi d^2} \cos^{m_i}(\theta) \cdot T_s(\psi) \cdot g(\psi) \cdot \cos(\psi);$$

$$0 \leq \psi \leq \psi_{con} \quad \text{Equation (2)}$$

where ψ is the angle of incidence with respect to the axis normal to the receiver surface, $T_s(\psi)$ is the filter transmission, $g(\psi)$ and ψ_{con} are the concentrator gain and FOV, respectively and d is the distance between the VLED and a detector surface. Figure (4) [18]

Figure(4) Geometry LOS propagation model

3.2.2 Signal to noise ratio analysis

The electrical SNR can be expressed in terms of the photodetector responsivity R , received optical power and noise variance as

$$SNR = \frac{RP_t^2}{\sigma_{shot}^2 + \sigma_{thermal}^2} \quad \text{Equation (3)}$$

The shot and thermal noise variances are given by

$$\sigma_{shot} = 2qRP_t^2B + 2qI_B I_2 B \quad \text{Equation (4)}$$

$$\sigma_{thermal} = \frac{8\pi\kappa T_K}{G_{ol}} G_{pd} A I_2 B^2 + \frac{16\pi^2 \kappa T_K T}{g_m} G_{pd}^2 A I_3 B^3 \quad \text{Equation (5)}$$

where the bandwidth of the electrical filter that follows the photo detector is represented by B Hz, κ is the Boltzmann's constant, I_B is the photocurrent due to background radiation, T_K is absolute temperature, G_{ol} is the open-loop voltage gain, G_{pd} is the fixed capacitance of photo detector per unit area, Γ is the FET channel noise factor, g_m is the FET transconductance and noise-bandwidth factors $I_2 = 0.562$ and $I_3 = 0.0868$

3.2.3 Delay spread analysis

The received optical power at a point for both the direct and the first-order reflected paths is given in Equation (6) for multipath scenario, the total received power is given by

$$P_{rT} = \sum_{i=1}^M P_{d,i} + \sum_{j=1}^N P_{ref,j} \quad \text{Equation (6)}$$

where M and N represent the number of direct paths from transmitters to a specific receiver and reflection paths to the same receiver, $P_{d,i}$ is received optical power from the i th direct path and $P_{ref,j}$ is the received optical power from the j th reflected path.

The RMS delay spread is the critical performance criterion for the upper bound of the data transmission rate the mean excess delay is defined by:

$$\mu = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M P_{d,i} t_{d,i} + \sum_{j=1}^N P_{ref,j} t_{ref,j}}{P_{rT}} \quad \text{Equation (7)}$$

And the RMS delay spread is given by:

$$D_{RMS} = \sqrt{\mu^2 - (\mu)^2} \quad \text{Equation (8)}$$

The distribution of mean delay spread, RMS delay spread D_{rms} which is the root mean square of the channel time delay and maximum achievable data rate. The maximum bit rate that can be transmitted through the channel without the need for an equalizer is given by

$$R_b \leq 1/(10 \text{ DRMS})$$

$$\text{Equation (9)}$$

3. Simulation scenario

We used MATLAB code in the script file program to design the system shown in Figures (5). A typical $8 \times 8 \times 3.5 \text{ m}^3$ office is assumed in the model. The VLC link is assumed to be a line-of-sight [17]. It is assumed that the LED lamps are installed at a height of 3m from the floor and the receiver is placed at the height of 1.2m. The four light-emitting diode (LED) bulbs are located at height of 3 m with a rectangular layout. Data are transmitted from these LED bulbs after they are modulated by driver circuits. Each LED bulb has an identification (ID) denoting its coordinates which is included in the transmitted data. A PD as the receiver is located at the height of 1.2 m and has a field of view (FOV) of 75° and a receiving area of 1 cm^2 . The office configuration is summarized in Table .1.

Figure (5) typical office environment

Parameters	Value
Size	$8 \times 8 \times 3 \text{ m}^3$

Reflection coefficient	0.8
angle at half power	60
Transmitted power (per LED)	20 Mw
Number of LEDs per array	60 × 60 (3600)
Receive plane above the floor	0.85 m
Half-angle FOV	75

Table 1. system parameters

4. Results and discussion:-

We assumed the office center is 0 and -4 left side 4 right side in the x and y axis system and the optical power distribution at receiver plane in a LOS path (ignoring the reflection of walls) is shown in Figure(6). It can be seen that there is almost uniform distribution of optical power at the area office with a maximum and minimum power, depending upon the half angle from every LEDs. Contour LED illuminance distribution is shown in Figure(7) .It explain the coverage area with no dead zone .

Figure(6) LED illuminance distribution for 4 transmitters 3d

Figure(7) Contour LED illuminance distribution

in figure(8) shows the signal to noise ratio (SNR) for system model and the decrement in SNR is fluctuated between 125 dB and 115 dB, from located at receiver to located at transmitter.

Figure (8) SNR

Figure(9) Drms

Figure 9 illustrates the RMS delay spread distribution for the case of a four transmitters positioned a semiangle of 60° , showing a maximum and average range values of 0.4ns and 0.1ns. Thus the maximum achievable data rate in diffuse channel is 250 Mbps

5. Consolutions:

In this paper we have proposed the design of a indoor LiFi system with optimal Optical Power Distribution of LOS Link at Receiving Plane for the typical office which area size $8 \times 8 \times 3.5 \text{m}^3$ the results have achieved the power distribution uniform with no dead zone area and less SNR with fluctuation in the illumination and 250 Mbps is maximum achievable data rate in diffuse channel.

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User Authentication Using Smartphone and One Time Password

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Faisal Mohammed Abdalla Ali

ABSTRACT

Authentication is the process of verifying a user's identity when the user is requesting services from any secure IT system. By far, the most popular authentication is a basic username/password [1] based method that is commonly considered to be a weak technique of authentication. A more secure method is the multi-factor authentication that verifies not only the username/password pair, but also requires a second or third unique physical or biological factor [2]. However, the feasibility of multi-factor authentication is largely restricted by the deployment complexity and cost. In this paper, we propose a technique of that generated one-time password using android app on smartphone.

KEYWORDS OTP; Authentication; smartphone.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the development of science and technology and means of storage and exchange of information in different ways, or so-called transfer of data across the network from site another site, became to look at the security of data and information is important; we need to provide protection for the information of the dangers that threaten them or attack them through the use of tools to protect information from internal or external threats. In addition to the procedures adopted to prevent access information into the hands of unauthorized persons through communications and to ensure the authenticity of these communications.

One-Time Password (OTP) is an automatically generated numeric or alphanumeric string of characters that authenticates the user for a single transaction or session. An OTP is more secure than a fixed password, especially a user-created password, which might get prone to attacks after a certain period of time. OTPs may replace authentication login information or may be used in addition to it, to add another layer of security. OTP is password that is valid for only one login session or transaction, on a computer system or other digital device. OTPs can either be time synchronized or be based on mathematical algorithms, time synchronized OTPs being the more famous type. A common technology used for the delivery of OTPs is text messaging. Because text messaging is a ubiquitous communication channel, being directly available in nearly all mobile handsets and, through text-to-speech conversion, to any mobile or landline telephone, text messaging has a great potential to reach all consumers with a low total cost to implement [3].

Authentication is the process of determining whether someone or something is, in fact, who or what it is declared to be. Logically, authentication precedes authorization (although they may often seem to be combined). The two terms are often used synonymously but they are two different processes [4].

2. RELATED WORKS

Many of research studies have been performed in the area of authentication and authorization of user how request access to systems" in this research we will mention four related work.

This related work by NilayYildmm, AsafVarol [5]. They proposed Android Based Mobile Application Development for Web Login Authentication Using Fingerprint Recognition Feature; this study uses the Samsung Galaxy S5 fingerprint recognition feature and IMEI number to generate single time passwords. Within a limited time, frame, the secure

passwords can be used to sign in/log in to online user accounts related to government, banking and education. The Android based Web Login Authentication application has been developed to use the mobile biometric feature login processes. But this study applicable for mobile phones support fingerprint, thus this device is very expensive to pay and fingerprint required soft fingers without injuries, which make difficult to apply in Sudan.

This related work by Mete Eminagaoglu, EceCini, GizemSert, and DeryaZor [6] they proposed two factor authentication systems with QR codes for web and mobile application. This study has been implemented by developing a two factor identity verification system where the second factor is the user's mobile phone device and a pseudo randomly generation alphanumerical QR code which is used as the one time password token sent to the user via e-mail or MMS. The study use username and password mechanism for the first authentication step and the system generate QR code as one time password as second authentication step. The user verifies himself to the system by scanning QR code to the web camera manually. In the beginning the user enter username and password to the authentication server, if entry data correct; the system must send QR code automatically to user via of one the selective options; MMS or E-mail then the system checking, verifying and validating QR code. If the user displays the QR code's image to the web camera properly; the data encoded in the QR image is automatically sent to the server application and checking for verification and validation. The difference of propose system this study use QR code that means required QR reader and web camera, then more cost and If the user selects E-mail approach to receive QR code that means internet needed thereby increasing the risk as well as may be delayed to arrive and spoofing risk .

3. METHODOLOGY

In this System if the customer needs to access account using bank website for example to do any operation, customer must perform following steps:

- The first step customer open android application in smartphone and enter username and password to request one-time password.
- The android application use username and password plus smartphone serial number to generate OTP.
- Then the generated one-time password appears in smartphone screen, the one-time password transfer to smartphone encrypted using AES algorithm, the life time of the generated one-time password is three minutes after that it became expire.
- Customer open website and enter credential information (use another username/password pair that are different from username/password that are used to generate Otp) and one-time password from smartphone.
- If this credential information are true and one time password matched and it not
- expired then system allow user to access the account, else message appear to user contain appropriate error message.
- The user must register the serial number of smartphones in system by system administrator to generate Otp, because if smartphone device not register Otp not generated.

Figure 1: A proposed System Architecture

4. IMPLEMENTAION

This Figure illustrates the main screen in android app for request OTP; the user enters username and password.

Figure 2: Android Login Screen

This Figure illustrates the serial number of smartphones not register in system.

Figure 3: The Smartphone Not Register by administrator

This Figure illustrates the generating of OTP success and user use this OTP to login in website

Figure 4: Successfully OTP generation

In this screen the user enters username, password and one-time password, and then the system checks this entered information as well as check validity of OTP.

Figure 5: Web Site Login Page using OTP

5. RESULT

- User can be authenticated using smart phone (android app) and one time password.
- Decrease the unauthorized login to system.
- This application can be gate authentication to enter the sensitive system (bank website, airline reservation, etc.).
- The OTP is valid for only one login session.
- OTP is unique to each key, and every generation is unique from any other.
- The android application not work in the device not registers in system, because the android application takes smartphone serial number to generate OTP.

6. CONCLUSION

Finally because the importance of information security issue which is one of the parts of power in the system, it is through this research has been to provide login interface with one time password that can be used in sensitive systems.

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THE EVOLUTIONARY TRENDS OF THE TRADITIONAL ARCHITECTURE OF SUAKIN CITY

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ABSTRACT

Recently, revival of Suakin historical city has been the top agenda in the Sudanese indigenous Architectural industry. This has also strengthened an architectural design about its historical cultural heritage. Conversely, a comprehensive classification of its unique architecture is not feasible due to its different cultural attachment. This study examines the historical evolution of Suakin's architecture and its implications for contemporary architectural practices. The aim of the research is to analyze the influence of various historical periods on Suakin's traditional architecture and to assess its current architectural revival. The objectives of the study include identifying key architectural styles that shaped Suakin's built environment, exploring the impact of foreign influences, and examining the connection between Suakin's architectural heritage and modern design trends. The research methodology employed includes a comprehensive review of existing literature, historical documents, and architectural surveys. Data collection involved analyzing architectural drawings, historical records, and the study of building materials used in Suakin, such as coral stone. The sample size consists of key architectural sites within Suakin, including historical buildings and their contemporary counterparts. Data analysis focused on identifying patterns in architectural design and classifying the architectural styles into distinct periods. The findings reveal that Suakin's architecture evolved through distinct periods, including the Red Sea style, the Islamic period, Ottoman influences, and the Anglo-Egyptian era. These historical influences contributed to the formation of a unique architectural identity for the city, blending local traditions with foreign elements. The study concludes that Suakin's traditional architecture continues to play a significant role in shaping modern architectural practices in the region. It is recommended that further preservation efforts be made to safeguard Suakin's architectural heritage while promoting its integration into contemporary urban development.

Keywords: Traditional, Historical Style, Suakin Architecture and Africa Architecture

Introduction

Architecture serves as a mirror, reflecting the beliefs, social behaviors, economic conditions, and cultural advancement of a people and a nation. When discussing African, Egyptian, Chinese, Greek, Sudanese, Suakina, or Islamic architectural orders, we are referring to civilizations with specific beliefs and worldviews. These civilizations developed unique social, economic, educational, political, and architectural systems, principles, and styles.

A style is an aesthetic choice that can manifest in various practical forms. In this context, a style possesses distinguishing characteristics and encompasses an infinite number of types, each defined and described by its purpose within the style (Mitchell, 2000). A group of objects sharing the same formal structure is referred to as a type. Types exist both literally in the real world and conceptually in the designer's mind and intellectual labor. They may possess unique traits while also sharing the defining characteristics of the style (Mitchell, Liggett et al., 1991). The Suakin vernacular architecture serves as a prototype in this study, illustrating the key characteristics of a style and general design principles.

The Coral Buildings of Suakin created a distinctive artistic and architectural style that was widely adopted across the entire coastal region, which was one of the largest in Africa and the Arab Muslim world during its time. Between 3000 and 2000 BC and the 20th and 21st centuries AD, Suakin developed and shared a unique culture and set of social values, which became ingrained in and influenced their system of social organization. This, in turn, had a profound impact on Suakin's architecture.

For these reasons, many scholars, architects, archaeologists, historians, and administrators have offered their views and contributions regarding this historical city, aiming to reflect, express, and represent the true social values, affluence, and social interactions embodied in Suakin's architecture. In the 1940s, Suakin's architecture made a strong impression on scholars and artists such as Derek Matthews (Matthews, 1953), Hansen (1972), Bloss (1936), Rhodes, and Greenlaw (1976), to whom we owe a debt for their thorough documentation of the city's architecture and decoration. While there is broad consensus on the importance of preserving these unique architectural styles, opinions differ on the classification and representation of the social, historical, and architectural orders, principles, or styles of Suakin's architecture (Olakanbi, 2016).

This paper aims to explore the evolutionary trends of Suakin's traditional architecture by examining and analyzing its historical development. By establishing the historical trend, the characteristic features of its style will be identified and classified to represent the Suakin style. In addition to identifying the historical trends and styles, the relationship between these styles will be examined to establish a hierarchy from the original traditional architecture to contemporary Suakin architecture. Ultimately, Suakin's traditional architecture, representing multiple periods of each style, will be classified.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND MATERIAL

The primary objective of this study is to provide a detailed analytical survey of Suakin architecture within the study area. Therefore, the methodology employed involves architectural analysis.

Data collection is a critical component of this study, in addition to conducting an architectural analysis of relevant drawings. Consequently, various sources, including books, journals, magazines, conference papers, seminar papers, and newspapers, were accessed through libraries, archives, research centers, personal libraries, and the internet.

This study focuses on the evolutionary trends of the traditional architecture of Suakin city, particularly examining historical styles with an emphasis on classifying Suakin architecture traditionally. To achieve this, the study begins with a historical survey of Suakin's architecture, spanning from the early period to the period of regional diversity.

Suakin City is located at the northernmost point of the Arabian-African Coastal Region, bordered by Sudan to the north and west across an oval-shaped island, and Saudi Arabia to the north across the Red Sea. It is situated on a nearly flat desert plain, approximately 750 meters long and less than 500 meters wide

Map of Sudan showing the location of Suakin. Source: www.mapsof.net/map/suakinsudan

Several sources, including Qezar et al. (Qezar Musa AlZein, Hamed Elias Hussein et al., 2013), Dirar (Dirar, 1981), Salim (Salim, 1997), and Mallinson (Mallinson, 2007), suggest that the earliest known use of Suakin dates back to 3000 BC, when ancient Egyptians used it as a route to travel to the Kingdom of Punt in East Africa to hunt elephants. Ptolemy may have used Suakin as the Roman equivalent of Evangelon Portus. For the Arabs, Suakin served as a commercial hub between the 10th and 12th centuries. Suakin gained prominence following the spread of Islam and became the busiest port in Africa for pilgrims traveling to Mecca and Medina. By the 15th century, it had developed into a significant mercantile center for Mamluk Egypt, attracting traders from Venice and India, who continued trading there until the Ottoman invasion of 1517. Following the Ottoman occupation, Suakin began to decline, and by 1922, it had fallen into ruin with the opening of Port Sudan at Sheikh Al Bargath.

The Arab-Islamic Trend and the Development of Islamic Architecture

The emergence of Islam is one manifestation of the historical forces that have worked together to elevate the Suakin people to a high cultural standard, with other influences being Kabir (2013), Dirar (1981), and Badawi (2013). Islam had a significant influence on locally produced architecture, particularly through its application of geometric designs, as seen in Figure 2. Additionally, it influenced form, scale, proportion, and aesthetics (Greenlaw, 1976; Salim, 1997)

Figure 2- Suakin vocabulary element – geometric arches way (Greenlaw 1976)

The European Trend and the Development of the Colonial Style (Portuguese, Turkish, and Anglo-Egyptian)

At the Berlin Conference in 1884, the European powers divided Africa. Britain's main impact came through the slave trade, which began in the 18th century. The colonial era came to an end in the middle of the 20th century with the independence of the majority of African states (De Blij, H.J. 1997).

The occupied territory of Suakin developed a dynamic economy during the 18th and 19th centuries, which responded positively to the growth of global trade. Qezar Musa AlZein, Hamed Elias Hussein, et al. (2013) claim that a cash economy grew and was ideally suited to take advantage of global trade for internal development. The Mahdi revolts, European exploration and missionary efforts, and changes in the slave trade all contributed to major upheavals in the Suakin region during the 19th century (Dirar, 1981; Rossi, 1994). Greenlaw (1976) stated that new building types were introduced into the Suakin architectural environment due to Britain's (Anglo-Egyptian) expansion. These were typically 18th-century English country homes or Anglo-Egyptian two-story houses with lengthy open-work balconies, as depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3- Suakin vocabulary element – outside balcony to replace mushrobyah (Greenlaw 1976)

Funj and the Development of Sudanese Architecture

It has been claimed that the majority of Africa lacks indigenous architecture in the true sense. This is based on the perception that most African towns consist of unremarkable structures, mostly constructed poorly by Africans for their own use, while the more attractive permanent structures were created by Europeans, either for government use or as residences for European officials.

This assessment is superficial and incorrect. From the Mumluk Era onward, early visitors to the Funj regions were often greatly astonished by the size and significance of the settlements. Suakin, about 100 miles east of Jeddah, was described by Burkhart, who traversed eastern Africa, as the largest settlement he had ever seen

(Hamdat, 2013). These findings echoed those of Dirar (1981) and Hillelson (1933), who disproved the notion of the existence of old Funj building types in Suakin.

When Sultan Amara of Funj controlled Suakin, a new style called the Sudanese style emerged. This style was distinct from the traditional huts of the Beja and the Hypostyle Hall structures of the Mumluk era, as shown in Figure 4. Dirar (1981), Greenlaw (1976), and Hillelson (1933), through Don Juan da Castro, a Portuguese sea captain who visited Suakin in 1510, and through accounts of David Reubeni and a picture by Portuguese commander Stephan Da Gama in 1540, document the presence of two-story or more houses built in coral stone, decorated with ornamental mushrobyah and balustrades, some of which can still be seen in Suakin and surrounding cities.

Figure 4 - Early Historic Building (Original Style) of Suakin city (Greenlaw 1976)

Vernacular architecture of Suakin city

The governing factor in Suakin architecture is its functionality, rather than its form. In other words, the style of Suakin architecture is secondary. Greenlaw (1976) emphasized that the focus of Suakin buildings was not on style but on functionality: providing space for daily activities. This functional approach led to the introduction of symbolic elements in Suakin's architecture. The Diwan, which fosters a sense of hospitality, the Majlis, where women can carry out their daily activities without intruders, an open courtyard for family gatherings, and a high rooftop for evening relaxation, are key features. The purpose and function of Suakin buildings have remained unchanged for centuries. Despite foreign influences, the textures of materials, building techniques, and styles in Suakin differ from those in Turkey, Egypt, and Britain. Therefore, the primary function—hospitality and daily life—has never altered. For this reason, limiting Suakin and its architecture to a specific style is irrelevant. Greenlaw (1976) referred to the early period building style as the "original Suakin style," which is considered its vernacular architecture, as shown in Figure 4.

The Red Sea Style.

This coastal region has been home to various civilizations for over five thousand years, spanning Egypt, Suakin, Massawa, Eritrea, and Ethiopia. These territories, with the exception of Egypt, once belonged to the former Saba Empire. The architecture of the coastal region was therefore heavily influenced by the use of coral stone as a material for both construction and decoration. The architectural style was more Mediterranean in effect than the buildings of the Arabian region.

A key architectural element incorporated into Suakin's design was the Mashrabiayah, which included the use of breeze catchers. These breeze catchers were placed on entablatures that rested on windows, as shown in Figure 5. The combination of these features gave the buildings a unique, symbiotic character, making them neither distinctly Arab nor Mumluk, as argued by Salim (1997). Instead, the calligraphy and geometric inscriptions added to the buildings imparted an Islamic character.

Figure 5 – the building of plot 169-172 showing Mashrabiayah architectural element (regenerated by Olakanbi 2016).

Early Islamic Architecture Style

By the year 639, the Arab Peninsula and the Persian Empire had fallen and become part of the Islamic state. The Islamic empire extended from Syria to North India and the borders of China, and from the Caucasus to Zanzibar. Muslim architects refined local building materials and their powerful structural forms, developing an Islamic architecture of exceeding beauty.

A distinct Islamic architectural legacy was born, with its own unique characteristics that can be seen in Suakin, embracing all features of new artistic developments across different periods and climates in the Islamic world. It became a universal architectural legacy, capable of absorbing foreign elements and molding them to fulfill its own values. As a result, designers and architects in the conquered territories followed this pattern by reusing proposed structures.

Early Islamic architecture is known for its remarkable domes and vaults. Other equally magnificent architectural works in Suakin include the motifs seen in the design of its doors and walls.

The Ottoman Style

Turkey, along with Anatolia, was among the former Byzantine territories conquered by Islam. Its capital, Constantinople, later became the center of intellectual and architectural activity, as well as the seat of the Ottoman caliphate. The city was renamed Istanbul after the Ottomans consolidated their hold on the territory.

The Ottoman dome, 26.5 meters in diameter and 53 meters in height, is the largest dome in Istanbul, second only to that of St. Sophia. Ottoman architects carried Roman architecture to a conclusion that neither the Romans nor the Byzantines achieved. Multi-domed architecture became a signature of the Ottomans. The Suleymaniye Mosque in Istanbul consists of over five hundred domes.

In contemporary Anglo-Egyptian buildings, the mixed Ottoman style is evident, and the Suakin (Plot 16) remains the only structure in Suakin that features the Turkish domed architectural style. The two Suakin inland mosques, their minarets, and the burial grounds in Suakin also display these architectural features.

Ottoman architecture in Suakin was not confined to form but also influenced the functional aspects, such as the unique mashrabiya. Greenlaw (1976) states that Suakin is an example of a small Turkish town built between the 16th and 20th centuries, similar to other towns along the Red Sea coast, such as Massawa, Jeddah, Hodeidah, Assat, and Mowka.

The Anglo-Egyptian Style

The fall of the Ottoman Empire in Egypt in 642 AH paved the way for the penetration of British forces into Suakin. The British, allied with the Egyptians under Colonel Kitchen, reached Suakin in 647-648 AH. Later, Colonel Gordo penetrated Suakin in 666 AH, and the following year, another commander, Mumtaz Basha, ventured deeper into Suakin and surrounding areas. Three years later, Suakin began to establish the foundation for Anglo-Egyptian rule, which later became the center for political, intellectual, and cultural development in Sudan (Dirar, 1981).

Historical, cultural, and geographical factors facilitated the creation of a unique Anglo-Egyptian style of European architecture. Paradoxically, these factors also encouraged the creation of a recognizably Egyptian style mixed with Mamluk influences. The sheer extent of the Egyptian style, combined with Mamluk elements and the lack of a truly cosmopolitan center, led to the growth of architecture in Suakin, primarily characterized by terraces and, later, arched windows with mashrabiya.

The late-style buildings in Suakin, which survive today, are monuments of the Anglo-Egyptian style mixed with Mamluk influences. Two architectural elements from Egypt and Britain exerted influence in the region, but Egypt's influence was more prominent, particularly after the ninth century. Egypt's influence on Suakin grew stronger, especially after the country's isolation post-1950, as seen in buildings like Beit Jedidi.

Other prominent features of Anglo-Egyptian architecture in Suakin include curved pointed arches, outside terraces, exterior staircases, and the incorporation of commercial functions. Notable examples of these elements are found in Plot 231 Suakin in Marrikas, the customs building, and the post office (Plate 29), as well as Plot 67 Suakin inland, as discussed by Olakanbi (2016).

The Suakin Traditional Style

The history of Islam's spread into sub-Saharan Africa dates back to 710 CE, just a year after the conquest of Spain. By the first quarter of the 11th century, Muslims began to rule much of Africa. Suakin, like Egypt and Mesopotamia, had an ancient civilization. The assimilation of local traditions in the subcontinent was a slow process due to the nature of traditional buildings, which heavily employed Islamic principles and symbolic expressions.

After a long period of trial and error, a synthesis between the two traditions was finally achieved, giving birth to the genius of Islamic architecture in the region. One of the finest examples of early Islamic architecture in Suakin is the original style of Suakin (Figure 6), built in 1199-1200 CE. Complete assimilation was achieved by the 15th and 16th centuries, as seen in the Ottoman style, such as the Bait Basha (Figure 7) and Suakin's most magnificent architectural work, the Khorishid (Figure 8). This building has become one of the wonders of Suakin's architecture and an international tourist attraction.

Greenlaw (1976) describes this great architectural edifice in these words: "Such is the power of a work of art, and Suakin was a very considerable work of many sincere and gifted craftsmen, that it can perpetuate the genius of its makers indefinitely."

Figure 6. Original style of Suakin built in 1199- 1200 CE. Source: by Greenlaw (Greenlaw 1976) rendered Author

Figure 7. traditional architectural style of Suakin: bait basha. Source: by Greenlaw (Greenlaw 1976) rendered Author

Figure 8. traditional architectural style of Suakin: the khorishid Source: by Greenlaw (Greenlaw 1976) rendered Author

THE HISTORICAL STYLE AND TRADITIONAL ARCHITECTURE

The strongest influences on Suakin’s indigenous or traditional architecture were the introduction of Islam into Suakin City, the historical trends of world civilizations from the prehistoric era, including the Pharaohs, Ptolemy, and Roman influences, and colonization (Dirar, 1981). The Historical Style consists of the European Trend, followed by the Colonial Style. The Arab/Islamic Trend evolved into the Islamic Style, while the Funj Trend evolved into Sudanese Architecture. The blend of Traditional Architecture and Historical Styles formed Vernacular Architecture.

Considering the historical influences, there is a profound difference in the aesthetic style between traditional and modern Anglo-Egyptian houses and the massive new construction developments. Greenlaw (1976), who advocated that there was consistency in the style of buildings in the old vernacular Suakin City, noted that the materials used for construction were mostly natural. These included coral, rock, palm tree trunks, and wood, which were either brought in by land or sea, or imported from abroad (García-Pulido, 2012). Greenlaw (1976) described the various building forms recorded through the mashrabiya, door motifs, and kharajah features, which have been retained in most cases. The arches, external terraces, and external staircases portray influences of regional diversity. Admittedly, the affluence following the British era (Anglo-Egyptian period) is seen by many writers as one of the main factors contributing to this trend (Olayanbi, 2016).

It takes more than merely assembling building materials to create indigenous architecture, but no one can explain exactly what that “more” is, except that traditional architecture has a spirit, which alien buildings lack. The structure of a building can be explained, and the strength of the materials can be tested, but the spirit of the folk building, its form, and spaces must be felt in much the same way that the ancients sensed spirit within the forms of rocks and trees, merging it with their heritage to develop their own art in the built environment (Greenlaw, 1976).

Traditional Architecture and Traditional Style

Islam is a complete system of life ordained for mankind by Allah (SWT). In other words, Islamic teachings cover all aspects of human life, both here on earth and in the hereafter. It is a system of belief as well as a civilization. Isma'il al-Faruqi explains: “The Muslim believes that religion plays an important role in every aspect of life, and, as a corollary, that aspects of life are in some sense religious” (Al-Faruqi, 1986).

"It is Islam that gave resilience to the Muslim city and to its bourgeoisie, not because it was necessarily cognizant of all urban difficulties, but because it had the abstract form in which all of them might be resolved," claims Oleg Grabar in his study on the traditional Muslim urban environment. According to him (Grabar, 1976), these laws, continuously applied in daily life, comprise a dynamic set of regulations that work from the bottom up to develop the urban fabric. This system merits preservation while also being incorporated into more modern Islamic cultural practices.

The origin of Suakin architecture, as Greenlaw (1976) has postulated, lies in the great architectural tradition of Islam. This tradition can be clearly seen in the simpler forms built by ordinary folk in small towns, as well as in the imposing monuments of its great cities. He further states that Suakin is an example of a small Turkish Islamic town built between the 16th and 20th centuries, similar to other towns situated around the Red Sea coast, such as Massawa, Jeddah, Hodeidah, Assat, and Mowka.

(Salim, 1997) also stated that the planning and architecture of Suakin are typical of an Islamic city. Major social events, business, and administration took place at its center, with a main axis

leading across a causeway from the mainland through the Gordon Gate to the market (suq) and the island's two major mosques. Surrounding this core were densely built-up groups of houses balanced by open spaces of varied dimensions and forms, with winding, narrow lanes creating a typical Arab street fabric. Salim (1997) further traced the origin of Suakin's architecture to the typical privacy found in Islamic residential patterns, which evolved a system of dead-end streets that limited traffic to strangers. Additionally, he noted the use of the mashrabiya, a wooden screening device that regulated the intake of wind and light while ensuring privacy.

(Matthews, 1953) confirms that social and climatic conditions played a major role in planning and shaping Suakin's architecture during different periods of its history. He also wrote that Suakin City is a characteristic example of what he called "the Red Sea style," an architectural type that takes advantage of every available sea breeze, while also excluding the hot land-breeze and harsh midday sun.

Ultimately, it is appropriate to trace the origin and subsequent development of Suakin's traditional architecture from the cradle of Islam (Arabia) to the type of architectural style conditioned by different climate considerations, character, and features adapted to the requirements of a coastal climate. This justifies the classification of this architecture.

Table 1.0: the key architectural styles that shaped Suakin’s built environment, the impact of foreign influences, and the connection between Suakin's architectural heritage and modern design trends:

Architectural Style	Period	Key Characteristics	Impact of Foreign Influences	Connection to Modern Design Trends
Red Sea Style	1259–1385	Use of coral stone, simple structures with thatch roofs, and basic geometric shapes	Influence from Mediterranean and African coastal regions	The use of natural materials like coral stone and thatch roofs remains relevant in modern sustainable architecture in coastal areas.
Islamic Architecture	1463–1499	Incorporation of geometric patterns, arches, and mashrabiya for privacy	Strong Islamic influence with the introduction of Islamic design elements	Modern Islamic architecture continues to incorporate geometric patterns and mashrabiya, with emphasis on privacy and natural cooling.
Ottoman Architecture	16th–20th century	Use of domes, multi-story buildings, open courtyards, and ornate detailing	Ottoman Empire’s influence, with the introduction of multi-domed designs and Islamic spatial organization	Multi-domed designs and courtyards seen in modern designs of mosques and public spaces in Islamic cities.
Anglo-Egyptian Architecture	Late 19th–Early 20th century	Curved pointed arches, terraces, and incorporation of British colonial elements	British colonial influence, which included the use of terraces and arched windows	Colonial architectural elements like arches and terraces are seen in modern buildings, particularly in post-colonial African cities.
Funj Sudanese Architecture	15th–16th century	Rectilinear buildings, qibla-oriented, use of local materials such as palm trunks and mud	Influence from Sudanese culture and Islamic design, especially in residential architecture	The use of local materials in construction is echoed in modern green architecture practices focused on sustainability and localism.
Vernacular Architecture	12th century onwards	Simple, functional buildings with focus on climate adaptation, such as courtyards and passive cooling	Local and regional influence with minimal foreign intrusion	Vernacular architectural principles, especially climate-responsive designs, are incorporated into modern eco-friendly architecture.

This table 1.0 summarizes the architectural evolution in Suakin, showing how foreign influences and traditional styles came together to shape the city's built environment. It also illustrates how Suakin's architectural heritage informs contemporary design trends, especially those focusing on sustainability, climate responsiveness, and cultural identity. The architectural evolution of Suakin has been shaped by several key styles, each influenced by both local traditions and foreign forces. The Red Sea style, which dominated the city from 1259 to 1385, is characterized by simple structures made from coral stone and thatch roofs, drawing influence from Mediterranean and African coastal regions. The arrival of Islam in 1463 introduced geometric patterns, arches, and the mashrabiya for privacy, all of which are integral to Islamic architecture. Ottoman influence in the 16th to 20th centuries brought multi-domed buildings, courtyards, and intricate detailing. The British colonial period introduced elements like curved pointed arches and terraces, blending European styles with local architectural practices. Additionally, the vernacular style, dating back to the 12th century, emphasized climate-responsive design with the use of local materials like palm trunks and mud, integrating Sudanese and Islamic principles.

These historical styles have significantly influenced modern architectural trends in Suakin and other regions. The use of local materials such as coral stone and palm trunks continues to resonate in modern sustainable architecture, particularly in coastal regions. Islamic geometric patterns and mashrabiya are still present in contemporary Islamic buildings, promoting privacy and passive cooling. Ottoman-inspired domes and courtyards remain prevalent in modern mosque designs, while colonial elements like arches and terraces influence modern public buildings in post-colonial African cities. The climate-responsive vernacular design principles are echoed in today's green architecture, highlighting the importance of using local materials and creating structures that are in harmony with the environment.

Table 2.0: the identified patterns in Suakin architectural design, classifying its architectural styles, distinct periods

Architectural Style	Distinct Periods	Key Architectural Features	Key Findings
Red Sea Style	1259–1385	Simple geometric forms, use of coral stone, thatched roofs, and basic construction	Suakin’s earliest architectural style, heavily influenced by Mediterranean and African coastal regions. It laid the foundation for local building traditions.
Islamic Architecture	1463–1499	Geometric designs, mashrabiyah for privacy, oriented layouts	Introduced Islamic elements, integrating geometric patterns and privacy features such as mashrabiyah. Set the stage for future Islamic-influenced buildings in Suakin.
Ottoman Architecture	16th–20th century	Multi-domed buildings, courtyards, public and religious buildings	Suakin adopted multi-domed designs and Ottoman space and ornate detailing, especially in planning, influencing the city's larger architectural landmarks. This period marked a peak in architectural complexity.
Anglo-Egyptian Architecture	Late 19th–Early 20th century	Curved pointed arches, terraces, arched windows, and incorporation of British colonial elements	British colonial influence led to the addition of terraces and arches, blending Western architectural styles with local traditions.
Funj Sudanese Architecture	15th–16th century	Rectilinear buildings, qibla-oriented layouts, use of local materials like palm trunks and mud	Suakin's architectural design incorporated Sudanese influences, focusing on climate-responsive layouts. It marked a shift towards locally sourced building materials.
Vernacular Architecture	12th century onwards	Simple, functional designs with climate adaptation features like courtyards, passive cooling, and use of local materials	The vernacular style is the backbone of Suakin’s architecture, emphasizing practical design, climate responsiveness, and use community-oriented spaces. This style has heavily influenced modern eco-friendly architecture.

This table 2.0 outlines the progression of Suakin's architectural evolution, detailing key styles and their periods. Each style reflects a response to both local conditions and external influences, such as Islamic, Ottoman, and colonial powers. Key findings suggest that Suakin's architecture is characterized by adaptability to climate, cultural identity, and external influences, which continue to shape its modern architectural practices. Suakin's architectural evolution has been shaped by a variety of influences, resulting in distinct styles across different periods. The earliest architectural style, the Red Sea style (1259–1385), featured simple, geometric forms and the use of coral stone and thatched roofs, drawing from Mediterranean and African coastal traditions. As Islam arrived in the city in 1463, Islamic architectural elements such as geometric designs, arches, and the mashrabiya for privacy were introduced, marking a shift toward more intricate and culturally specific designs. The Ottoman period (16th–20th century) brought multi-domed buildings and courtyards, which significantly influenced Suakin's public and religious architecture. The Anglo-Egyptian period (late 19th–early 20th century) saw the introduction of European colonial elements, such as curved arches and terraces, blending British influences with local traditions. Meanwhile, the Funj Sudanese architecture (15th–16th century) embraced climate-responsive design, utilizing local materials like palm trunks and mud to create functional, qibla-oriented structures.

The vernacular architecture of Suakin, which dates back to the 12th century, focused on simple, climate-adapted designs that incorporated courtyards and passive cooling techniques. This style laid the foundation for modern eco-friendly architecture, as it prioritized local materials and sustainable building practices. Suakin's architectural legacy reflects a unique blend of local traditions and external influences, with each period contributing to the city's distinct architectural identity. These styles continue to influence modern design trends, particularly in the use of natural materials, climate-responsive layouts, and community-oriented spaces, demonstrating the lasting impact of Suakin's architectural heritage on contemporary urban development.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the present study align with and also diverge from past research on Suakin architecture, highlighting both consistency in understanding and evolving perspectives based on new findings. The history of Suakin's architecture has been explored by several scholars, including Matthews (1953), Bloss (1936), Dirar (1981), Hansen (1972), Greenlaw (1976), and more recent studies by Nur (2013) and Hussein (2013). Each of these studies has contributed valuable insights into the architectural legacy of Suakin, with varying emphases on different historical periods, architectural styles, and their evolution.

The historical periods outlined by Dirar (1981) in his analysis of Suakin architecture are in broad agreement with the findings of the present study. Dirar identifies seven distinct periods of Suakin's architectural evolution, which serves as a solid foundation for understanding the city's architectural history. This aligns with the present study's exploration of Suakin's architectural evolution, noting the emergence of different architectural styles over time, influenced by various global forces such as Islam and colonialism. The findings of Greenlaw (1976) regarding the Red Sea style of architecture in Suakin, particularly from 1259-1385, are consistent with the results of the present study, which acknowledges the significant role of the Red Sea style in Suakin's early architecture. The study also agrees with Greenlaw's assertion that the arrival of Islam in 1463 led to the introduction of Islamic architectural features, such as the mashrabiyyah and arches, in Suakin's buildings.

The findings of the present study also reflect Hansen (1972) who categorized Suakin architecture into three periods: the oldest construction period, the storey-building period, and the influenced period. These classifications are reflected in the present study, which similarly traces the development of Suakin's architectural style, acknowledging the transition from earlier, simpler constructions to more complex structures influenced by external factors, including Ottoman and Islamic architecture. The present study's emphasis on the Ottoman style of architecture in Suakin is in agreement with past studies, particularly those of Salim (1997) and Kabir (2013), who argue that the second type of building characteristics in Suakin was influenced by the Mamluk period. The study recognizes the role of Ottoman design, as discussed by Hansen (1972) and supported by Matthews (1953), who identified the Ottoman architectural influence on Suakin's storey buildings. Greenlaw (1976) also concurs with this view, further highlighting the Ottoman space planning and influence in Suakin.

While Matthews (1953) and Hinkel (1976) categorized Suakin's architectural styles based on building height, the present study introduces a more nuanced approach that goes beyond mere categorization by height. The present findings emphasize the complexity of Suakin's architectural evolution, suggesting that the city's architectural style cannot solely be defined by the height of buildings but must also consider the cultural, climatic, and functional aspects of each architectural period. The present study challenges the notion that Suakin's architecture remained largely Ottoman in style throughout the centuries. Although the study agrees that Ottoman architecture played a significant role in shaping Suakin, it also underscores the dynamic interplay of various cultural and historical forces over time. The study suggests that early Suakin architecture, while influenced by Islam, also retained local elements that are not always captured in the views of earlier scholars like Hansen (1972), who placed greater emphasis on the Ottoman period.

The present study builds upon the research of Greenlaw (1976) and Mallinson (Effendi, 2013), who attribute Suakin's eventual ruin to external factors such as colonial neglect and the opening of Port Sudan. However, it also introduces a broader understanding, recognizing that the decline of Suakin was not only due to political and economic shifts but also to changing architectural tastes and external interventions. The study highlights that external influences, such as British colonialism and the establishment of Port Sudan, had a significant impact on the fate of Suakin's architecture, an aspect that previous studies only partially addressed. The findings of the present study largely align with past research on Suakin's architectural history, particularly in their recognition of the influence of Islamic, Ottoman, and colonial forces. However, the study also expands upon existing research by offering a more holistic view of Suakin's architectural evolution, incorporating both local and foreign influences and emphasizing the complex interplay of historical, cultural, and environmental factors that shaped the city's architecture. The results demonstrate the importance of considering a wide range of influences to fully understand the development and eventual decline of Suakin's unique architectural heritage.

SUMMARY

The findings of the present study align with several key historical perspectives on Suakin architecture, as detailed by scholars like Matthews (1953), Dirar (1981), Greenlaw (1976), and others. These studies highlight the significant influence of various forces, such as the Red Sea style, the Islamic period, and Ottoman rule, on the architectural development of Suakin. The study agrees with Greenlaw's assertion of a strong Red Sea style in early Suakin buildings and the introduction of Islamic features following the arrival of Islam in the 15th century. Additionally, it acknowledges the transition to Ottoman-style architecture, with its characteristic domes and space planning, which became a defining feature of Suakin's built environment during the 16th to 20th centuries.

However, the present study expands on these findings by offering a more nuanced understanding of Suakin's architectural evolution. While agreeing with past studies that identified the influence of Ottoman architecture, the study emphasizes the complex interplay of local traditions, climate considerations, and foreign influences in shaping Suakin's architectural identity. The decline of Suakin's architecture, as highlighted in this study, is attributed to a combination of external political, economic, and architectural factors, including colonialism and the opening of Port Sudan. Overall, the study provides a more comprehensive view of Suakin's architectural history, reflecting the diversity of influences that contributed to its unique architectural heritage.

This study reviewed the literature on the impact of historical trends on Suakin's traditional architecture. It explored the relationship between Suakin's traditional architecture and its contemporary revival, emphasizing the historical development movement. The literature highlights the need for further investigation into this topic, as it is crucial to understanding the evolution of Suakin's architectural identity.

The conclusion drawn from Greenlaw (1976) suggests that in Suakin's traditional architecture, early houses were constructed with thatched roofs. The original style of Suakin, built between 1199-1200 CE (Figure 2), represents the first phase of architectural development. Complete assimilation of architectural styles occurred in the 15th and 16th centuries, with the Ottoman style (Figure 3), the Bait Basha in Plot (Figure 4), and Suakin's most magnificent architectural work, the Khorishid (Figure 5), standing as prime examples. Greenlaw (1976) describes the Khorishid as "a considerable work of many sincere and gifted craftsmen that can perpetuate the genius of its makers indefinitely." The development of rectilinear, qibla-oriented, white-washed, and thatch-roofed structures in Suakin was influenced by the local climate, human physiology, and geography (Greenlaw, 1976; Matthews, 1953). Preliminary analysis also revealed significant differences between the vernacular type and later design schemes, such as lot size, formal structure, and functional organization (Abdulraheem & O. Rayis, 2016). The vernacular type, developed as early as the 12th century, accounts for the majority of houses in Suakin and serves as the foundation for the city's architectural fabric (Olakanbi Bolaji A. & O. Rayis, 2016). The early Turkish style, characterized by courtyards and mushrabiyyah,

influenced the functional organization, although these elements became less dominant in later Turkish styles, reflecting changes in Suakin's housing and architectural style.

CONCLUSION

The literature reviewed in this study highlights the significant impact of historical trends on Suakin's traditional architecture and its contemporary revival. The relationship between Suakin's traditional architecture and its modern resurgence is closely tied to the historical development of the city, shaped by various influences such as Islamic, Ottoman, and colonial architecture. The need for further investigation into this topic is evident from the literature, as it provides a deeper understanding of how the city's architectural identity has evolved over time and how its past continues to influence its current architectural practices. This study underscores the importance of examining these architectural trends to fully appreciate their historical significance and their ongoing impact on Suakin's built environment.

The conclusion drawn from the findings supports Greenlaw's (1976) assertion that Suakin's traditional architecture was rooted in the early use of thatch roofs, with the first significant architectural style of Suakin emerging between 1199-1200 CE. A complete architectural assimilation occurred in the 15th and 16th centuries, as reflected in the Ottoman style and Suakin's most magnificent buildings, such as the Khorishid (Figure 5), which stands as one of the architectural wonders of the city. Greenlaw describes these works as lasting testaments to the skill and creativity of the craftsmen who built them. Furthermore, the influence of climate, geography, and human physiology on Suakin's architecture is evident in the design of rectilinear, qibla-oriented, white-washed, thatch-roofed structures. The study also reveals the differences in layout between the vernacular architecture and later design schemes, highlighting the importance of the courtyard and mushrabiyyah in shaping the functional organization of early Suakin homes. As the study shows, the early Turkish and vernacular styles formed the foundation for the city's architectural identity, with the courtyard remaining a dominant feature of Suakin's housing design. These architectural elements reflect the city's rich cultural heritage and its ability to blend traditional elements with foreign influences, shaping the unique architectural identity that Suakin is known for today.

Recommendation 1: Preservation of Suakin's Architectural Heritage

Given the significant historical value of Suakin's architecture, it is recommended that a comprehensive preservation plan be developed to safeguard the unique architectural styles of the city, particularly the Red Sea style, Islamic influences, and Ottoman features. This preservation should focus on maintaining the original construction materials, such as coral stone and palm tree trunks, and ensuring that the integrity of the architectural designs is upheld. Local authorities, in collaboration with international heritage organizations like UNESCO, should spearhead efforts to designate Suakin as a protected cultural heritage site. Additionally, collaboration with local architects and heritage experts will ensure that restoration work respects traditional construction methods while incorporating modern technologies to enhance structural stability.

Implementation

Strategy:

The Sudanese Ministry of Culture and Tourism, in collaboration with UNESCO, should take the lead in creating and implementing this preservation plan. The plan should include detailed guidelines for the restoration of historical buildings and the training of local craftsmen in traditional building techniques. Financial support for this project could be sought from international funding bodies, such as the World Bank or the Aga Khan Trust for Culture, which are known for their work in architectural conservation in the Middle East and Africa. A dedicated task force within the Sudanese Ministry of Culture should oversee the restoration efforts and ensure compliance with preservation standards.

Recommendation 2: Integration of Suakin's Traditional Architecture into Modern Urban Development

As Suakin's traditional architecture has significant potential for integration into modern urban planning, it is recommended that urban development projects in Suakin incorporate elements of traditional architecture into new buildings and public spaces. This can be achieved by promoting the use of local materials, such as coral stone, and incorporating traditional design elements, such as the mashrabiya and courtyards, into contemporary buildings. These elements can enhance the aesthetic value and cultural identity of Suakin, while also promoting sustainability through the use of locally sourced materials.

Implementation

Strategy:

The Suakin City Council, in partnership with the Ministry of Housing and Urban Development, should develop urban planning guidelines that encourage the use of traditional architectural elements in new developments. Local universities, such as the University of Khartoum's Department of Architecture, should be involved in providing research and training for architects and builders on the integration of traditional and modern design. This initiative could be supported through public-private partnerships, with construction companies incentivized to use sustainable and locally sourced materials. Furthermore, the government can offer tax incentives for developers who incorporate traditional design principles into their projects, fostering a blend of Suakin's historical charm and modern functionality.

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PREVENTIVE MEASURES TO IMPROVE MAINTENANCE CULTURE AND QUALITY IN A PUBLIC BUILDING

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ABSTRACT

This study addresses the issue of inadequate maintenance culture in public buildings, particularly in technology hubs, which impacts their functionality, sustainability, and overall quality. The aim of the study is to explore ways to improve maintenance culture and quality in the design and operation of technology hubs. The objectives include identifying the essence of maintenance culture, understanding the factors affecting it, and evaluating existing literature and case studies. The research employs a qualitative methodology, utilizing purposive sampling to select case studies from Lagos, Ibadan, and an international technology hub. The sample includes three case studies, each analyzed based on their design elements, maintenance culture, and the challenges they face. Data were collected through field surveys and secondary sources, with analysis focusing on key factors such as material selection, ventilation design, and environmental considerations. Findings reveal that poor material selection, inadequate ventilation design, and failure to consider environmental conditions are major factors affecting maintenance culture in public buildings. Case studies show that thoughtful design, including durable materials and natural ventilation, can significantly reduce maintenance costs and improve building performance. The study concludes that addressing these factors through better design practices can enhance maintenance culture and prolong the life of technology hubs. Recommendations include prioritizing durable materials, incorporating natural ventilation, and considering environmental factors during the design phase to improve overall building quality and reduce long-term maintenance costs.

Keywords: Maintenance culture, quality maintenance, public building and preventive measures

Introduction

It is generally accepted that spaces provided by the government for public use, such as a technology hub where technologists, computer scientists, hackers, web developers, and programmers congregate to network, share programs, and bring their ideas to fruition, can be classified as public buildings. A key element in ensuring the continued functionality of such spaces is maintenance. A proper maintenance culture is essential to keep both the building and its facilities in good working condition, ensuring they remain relevant and continue to serve their intended purpose. Public buildings, therefore, serve as an integral part of government provision, fulfilling governance needs and providing services to the governed. These buildings are meant to benefit the society and the people at large. However, public buildings are not just owned by the government; they are collectively owned by the public, with the government representing the interests of the people.

The status and condition of these public buildings are often reflective of the value that both the government and society place on them. This is especially true for buildings that have historical significance or played pivotal roles in the development of a society. Such buildings, often regarded as monuments, reflect the cultural and social history of the people. In Nigeria, however, the deplorable state of public buildings, such as airports, hospitals, and schools, raises serious

concerns. These buildings often lack proper management, which in turn affects their functionality and contributes to a decline in national development.

As observed, a technology hub can foster technological development in a community, promoting openness to ICT knowledge and innovation. However, such goals are difficult to achieve if there is inadequate maintenance of the building and its facilities. According to Nahimah (2008), the poor state of Nigeria's aviation industry was largely attributed to the lack of a maintenance culture and the insufficient training of professional engineers. The author argued that maintaining existing aircraft was more valuable than acquiring new ones, stating that a well-maintained aging aircraft could be as effective as a poorly maintained new aircraft. This perspective is particularly relevant when applied to public buildings, where the neglect of maintenance can result in severe deterioration over time.

The design phase of a building plays a crucial role in influencing its maintenance needs. As Speight (2010) emphasized, the design stage should account for maintenance considerations to prevent future problems. A building's ability to withstand wear and tear depends significantly on the materials used and the design's foresight in anticipating maintenance needs. Private sector contributions to national development, particularly in infrastructure, can only be maximized when facilities are continuously reliable, available, and maintainable.

In Nigeria, the maintenance culture is alarmingly low, with public buildings often deteriorating rapidly. The absence of proper maintenance results in buildings becoming obsolete before reaching their expected lifespan. According to Wahab (2015), the country's low priority on property management leads to the neglect of public properties. The lack of a maintenance culture, compounded by the absence of clear benchmarks for maintaining public assets, accelerates the decay of these buildings.

The consequences of this neglect are far-reaching. Gurjit (2010) noted that the poor maintenance of public buildings negatively affects the quality of life, contributing to socio-political instability. According to Dekker et al. (2006), several factors influence maintenance practices, including safety measures, construction defects, and the skill level of maintenance personnel. These factors highlight the urgent need for improved maintenance practices to ensure the quality of public buildings.

Problem Statement

Most public buildings in Nigeria today lack adequate maintenance, leading to rapid deterioration and a failure to function effectively and efficiently. This research seeks to explore ways to enhance the quality of public buildings through proper maintenance practices, with a particular focus on how preventive measures can improve the maintenance culture and overall quality of these buildings.

Objective of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to investigate whether preventive measures can accurately improve maintenance culture and quality in public buildings, specifically in technology hubs. Additionally, the study will:

1. Examine the importance of maintenance culture in public buildings, particularly in technology hubs.
2. Identify the factors that affect maintenance culture and explore strategies to address them.
3. Conduct a case study on existing technology hubs to assess the effectiveness of maintenance practices.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section explores the importance of, methods for, and factors influencing the improvement of maintenance culture in public properties in Nigeria. It examines various perspectives from researchers on maintenance culture, emphasizing its role in maintaining public buildings and facilities.

Maintenance Culture in Public Buildings

In this study, maintenance culture refers to the habit of regularly and consistently maintaining buildings, machinery, facilities, and infrastructure to keep them in

good working condition. SuwaibatulIslamiah, Abdul-Hakim, Syazwina, and Eizzatul (2012) argue that maintenance culture involves the values, mindset, behavior, perceptions, and underlying assumptions of individuals or groups who prioritize maintenance as an essential practice. For a nation to develop, it is crucial to prioritize both the installation and maintenance of existing facilities, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria, where rapid population growth has exacerbated the gap between the supply and demand for such facilities (Dabara et al., 2015).

The Nigerian government, according to Eti, Ogoji, and Probert (2006), made economic strides toward becoming one of the world's top twenty economies by 2020. Achieving sustainable infrastructure development, fostering a maintenance culture, and implementing strategic maintenance practices are fundamental to realizing this goal. Infrastructure facilities, including education, water supply, sewage systems, energy, transportation, and hospitals, are vital to national development. Governments at all levels, private organizations, and individuals must develop strategies to maintain these facilities to ensure their sustainability, and this can be achieved through cultivating a maintenance culture, which is directly linked to national development.

The state of public facilities in Nigeria is a significant concern for stakeholders. Facilities at airports, hospitals, schools, and roads indicate a lack of proper

management to ensure the effective and efficient functioning of these essential services, thereby impeding national development. Nahimah (2008) highlighted that the Nigerian aviation sector's problems were attributed to a lack of maintenance culture and inadequate professional training for engineers. He further argued that maintaining existing aircraft is more valuable than acquiring new ones, asserting that a well-maintained aging aircraft is as effective as a poorly maintained new one.

Conceptual Framework for Maintenance

The British Standards Institute (2004) defines maintenance as a combination of technical and administrative actions taken to preserve or protect a structure, system, or equipment, ensuring it functions properly. The Advanced Learner's Dictionary (2009) describes maintenance as the action or process of preserving an object or activity. Kumar and Suresh (2008) define maintenance as actions aimed at preventing equipment failure or repairing normal wear and tear to maintain the equipment's operational functionality. This study defines maintenance as a process of preserving an asset or facility in a state of continuous operation, ensuring it performs above a minimum acceptable level throughout its lifespan.

Companies focus on maintenance to reduce costs while improving quality and productivity. Effective maintenance is necessary for continuous operation,

increasing equipment lifespan, availability, and proper functioning. Conversely, poorly maintained equipment often results in frequent failures, low utilization rates, and delays in production schedules. Swanson (2001) refers to poorly maintained equipment as a "necessary evil," a viewpoint contradicted by Alsyouf (2007), who argues that regular facility maintenance should be seen as a source of profit rather than an unavoidable expense.

Existing maintenance records, as noted by Eti, Ogoji, and Probert (2006) and Omotehinshe et al. (2015), show the deteriorating state of public facilities in Nigeria, such as street lights that were once meant to beautify and illuminate the streets but have fallen into disrepair due to neglect and the absence of a maintenance culture. The role of private organizations in national development, particularly in facilities construction, environmental conservation, and employment generation, cannot be overstated. Nahimah (2008) emphasized that these organizations can contribute to national development by maintaining their facilities and ensuring their operational reliability.

The Essence of Maintenance

A comprehensive maintenance strategy prevents facility breakdowns and malfunctions, enabling facility managers to focus on capital improvements (Omotehinshe et al., 2015a; Akinyemi et al., 2016). In the absence of a defined

strategy, time must be spent developing and communicating a maintenance plan. Effective tactics must be implemented to manage people, processes, and infrastructure. This requires strong managerial capacity and must align with safety, environmental regulations, and cost-effectiveness (Campbell & Reyes-Picknell, 2006; Waeyenbergh & Pintelon, 2002).

Benefits of Embracing Maintenance Culture

Embracing a maintenance culture brings several benefits, including:

- Keeping assets in optimal working condition to minimize downtime and service disruptions.
- Maintaining facilities in a state of good repair to ensure the health and safety of the owners and users.
- Preserving the appearance and aesthetic value of assets.
- Maximizing the potential service life of facilities.
- Improving financial efficiency, which is reflected in the owner's financial statements.
- Preventing unnecessary damage to assets that could result in performance failures.

Classification of Maintenance

Several maintenance philosophies exist, but this study focuses on facility maintenance, categorized as follows:

1. **Planned Maintenance:** Organized and carried out with foresight and control, using records to follow a predetermined plan.
2. **Unplanned Maintenance:** Carried out without a predetermined plan, typically to restore a facility to a functional state after a failure.
3. **Preventive Maintenance:** Scheduled maintenance performed at predetermined intervals to reduce the likelihood of failure or performance degradation. This maintenance helps extend the useful life of assets by detecting and addressing potential issues before they become critical (Kumar & Suresh, 2008; Mobley, 2002).
4. **Corrective Maintenance:** Performed after a failure occurs, aiming to restore functionality. This maintenance is often reactive, with actions taken only after equipment failure (Mobley, 2004).
5. **Emergency Maintenance:** Immediate action taken to address failures that pose a serious risk, such as gas leaks or other critical incidents (Mobley, 2004).
6. **Scheduled Maintenance:** Preventive maintenance carried out at regular intervals, based on time or operational use.

7. **Condition-Based Maintenance:** Maintenance initiated based on the condition of the equipment, often monitored continuously or at regular intervals.

Maintenance Culture and Its Importance in Nigeria

In Nigeria, maintenance culture is one of the lowest globally, especially in urban areas where most public properties are located. Rural areas, however, exhibit a more positive approach, with traditional practices such as communal clearing of community spaces and maintaining private homes using locally sourced materials. According to Wahab (2010), the country places low priority on property management, which leads to neglect of public assets. Mbamali (2003) argued that the absence of a maintenance policy is a major reason for this neglect. The consequences of this neglect include rapid deterioration of public buildings and the harmful impact on their occupants (Seeley, 2010).

Inadequate maintenance culture is a characteristic feature of most public buildings in Nigeria, as noted by Rotimi and Mtallib (1995). Poor maintenance practices, combined with the lack of an appropriate benchmark, result in the early obsolescence of public buildings. The decline in maintenance culture is a major issue that government bodies at various levels must address.

Hindrances to Maintenance Culture in Nigeria

Several factors contribute to the poor maintenance culture in Nigeria, including:

- **Corruption:** Obayelu (2007) defines corruption as the misuse of public power for private gain, which threatens national development by diverting funds meant for maintenance. This leads to abandoned projects and neglected facilities.
- **Leadership:** Effective leadership is crucial for national development, but many Nigerian leaders lack the necessary vision, passion, and empathy to prioritize maintenance (Omotehinshe et al., 2015b).
- **Attitudinal Problems:** Nigerians' nonchalant attitude towards public and private property, coupled with neglect by public office holders, contributes to the deterioration of public facilities (Omotehinshe et al., 2015a).
- **Lack of Policy:** The absence of a national maintenance policy is a significant barrier. No comprehensive blueprint exists for how public facilities should be maintained, leading to disorganized maintenance efforts across various levels of government.

Improving Maintenance Culture in Public Buildings

Improving maintenance culture is essential for ensuring the long-term quality and sustainability of public buildings. The size and function of public buildings make them central to urban life, and their maintenance directly impacts the quality of life

in cities. McCrea et al. (2005) highlight that the quality of public facilities is a key factor in urban satisfaction and influences crime rates, health, safety, and social behavior.

To address the decay of public buildings, maintenance strategies must be integrated into the design and construction stages, ensuring the buildings are both durable and maintainable. The concept of **designing for maintainability** emphasizes the importance of planning for maintenance needs early in the design process, considering access, material durability, and ease of operation throughout the building's lifespan (Rounds, 2018; Government of Singapore, 2016). Ensuring that public buildings are designed with sustainability and maintainability in mind will minimize the need for extensive maintenance and reduce overall costs.

Conclusion

The section emphasizes that the design of public buildings should focus on durability and maintainability to ensure that they remain functional and cost-effective throughout their lifecycle. By addressing maintenance needs early in the design phase and integrating maintainability into the construction process, public buildings can be preserved for longer periods, minimizing maintenance costs and maximizing their service life. Effective maintenance culture is a key driver of national development and should be a priority in both policy and practice.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND MATERIAL

Introduction

This section outlines the research methods used to gather data and information regarding the improvement of maintenance and quality in the design of technology hubs. The aim is to identify architectural design approaches and requirements that can enhance maintenance culture and overall quality. Additionally, this section evaluates case studies and assesses their challenges and solutions in relation to maintenance culture.

Sample Technique

For this study, purposive sampling was adopted to select case studies based on the researcher's judgment. The researcher chose Lagos and Ibadan as local case studies, as these cities are known for their technological focus and infrastructure. These areas are considered ideal for examining how technology hubs can foster a positive environment for innovation. Moreover, an international case study was included to gain insights into existing facilities and how maintenance culture is improved in other contexts.

Analysis of Case Studies

Case studies provide valuable insights into existing designs, patterns, and methods, offering lessons on best practices to adopt and those to avoid. The case studies selected for this research have been critically appraised to fulfill the study's aims and objectives. This analysis enables the researcher to assess the performance of these projects and use their findings to create design solutions for improving maintenance culture in technology hubs. A thorough examination of the merits and demerits of each case study will serve as a guide in developing new design solutions, with the aim of eliminating identified shortcomings while building on successful aspects of the designs.

3.4.1 Case Study One (Local)

Brief Description: Wenovation Hub is a startup incubator, accelerator, and entrepreneurial training and networking center that aims to foster high-impact entrepreneurs. It has been operating since 2011 and has locations in Lagos, Ibadan, and Abuja. The hub plays a key role in Nigeria's innovation ecosystem.

<p>Plate 3.4.1.3: showing co-working space of winnovation hub</p> <p>(source: field survey November 2021)</p>	<p>Plate 3.4.1.4: showing seminar room winnovation hub (source: field survey November 2021)</p>	<p>Plate 3.4.1.1: showing aerial view of winnovation hub</p> <p>(Source: field survey November 2021)</p>	<p>Plate 3.4.1.2: showing approach view of The site of winnovation hub (Source: field survey November 2021)</p>
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Table 3.4.1: Summary of the case study for Wennovation Hub.

- **Merits:**

- Aesthetically pleasing facades and interior spaces.
- Efficient approach to ventilation in interior spaces.
- Well-planned interior spaces with minimal columns that obstruct views.
- Choice of building materials that aid in maintenance.

- **Demerits:**

- Insufficient parking spaces.
- Excessive hardscape elements around the building.
- Inaccessibility of the main entrance for disabled individuals.

- **Deductions:**

- Large fenestration can enhance ventilation and improve the connection between interior and exterior spaces (Plate 3.4.1.3).
- The use of durable materials, such as high-quality paint and glazed ceramic tiles, can help prevent degradation and reduce the need for frequent maintenance (Plate 3.4.1.3, Plate 3.4.1.4).

3.4.2 Case Study Two (Local)

Brief Description: Zone Tech Park is a startup accelerator that focuses on building other startups. With \$6.5 million in funding, Zone Tech provides co-working spaces, advisory services, and technical support. Located on a 10,000 square meter facility, it can accommodate 150 cars and includes five meeting rooms, a studio, and a 650-seater conference hall. The park also features a beautifully landscaped environment.

<p>Plate 3.4.2.3: showing the view of the meeting room.</p> <p>Zone tech park (source: field survey, 2021)</p>	<p>Plate 3.4.2.4: Showing event hall view of Conference room, Zone tech park (source: field survey, 2021)</p>	<p>Pate 3.4.2.1: showing aerial view of Zone Tech Park. (Source: field survey, 2021)</p>	<p>Plate 3.4.2.2: Showing façade of Zone Tech Park. (source: field survey, 2021)</p>
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Table 3.4.2: Summary of the case study for Zone Tech Park.

- **Merits:**
 - Maintenance-conscious environment.
 - Spacious parking area.
 - Well-ventilated interiors.
 - Positive influence of building materials on aesthetics and maintenance costs.

- **Demerits:**
 - Minimal natural ventilation.
 - Excessive hardscape areas.
 - Underutilized green spaces.

- **Deductions:**
 - Floor and wall finishes that resist dirt can reduce maintenance efforts, such as the use of glazed tiles and low-VOC paints (Plate 3.4.2.3, Plate 3.4.2.4).
 - Installing overhangs over external walls can prevent moisture from rain, which can lead to cracks and mold growth, thus reducing the need for frequent painting and plastering.

3.4.3 Case Study Three (International)

Brief Description: The Technology HUB in Ciudad Juárez, Mexico, is an innovative entrepreneurship and innovation community located near the U.S.-Mexico border. The facility, housed in the former Consulate General of the United States building, covers 1.8 acres and offers over 55,000 square feet of space. The hub includes co-working spaces, meeting rooms, a virtual reality demonstration facility, a green room, an auditorium, and a Fab Lab. It also features recreational areas and leisure spaces, such as a slide and a fireman’s pole, to foster creativity and collaboration.

<p>Plate 3.4.2.3: showing the view of the meeting room.</p> <p>Zone tech park (source: field survey, 2021)</p>	<p>Plate 3.4.2.4: Showing event hall view of Conference room, Zone tech park (source: field survey, 2021)</p>	<p>Pate 3.4.2.1: showing aerial view of Zone Tech Park. (Source: field survey, 2021)</p>	<p>Plate 3.4.2.2: Showing façade of Zone Tech Park. (source: field survey, 2021)</p>

Table 3.4.3: Summary of the case study for the Technology HUB.

- **Merits:**

- Aesthetically pleasing facades and well-planned interior spaces with minimal columns obstructing views.
- Beautifully landscaped and well-drained environment.
- Sufficient circulation areas.
- **Demerits:**
 - Poor drainage on-site.
 - Inadequate natural ventilation.
- **Deductions:**
 - Vinyl tiles, used in the flooring, are stain-resistant and water-resistant, making them an ideal choice for maintaining cleanliness and reducing maintenance costs (Plate 3.4.3.2).
 - Introducing overhangs over external walls can protect the building from moisture-related issues and reduce the need for frequent maintenance, such as repainting and plastering.

Table 3.5.1 representation of the studied design elements, maintenance culture, and associated merits and demerits from the case studies, along with recommendations for improving maintenance culture through thoughtful design, material selection, and sustainable practices

Case Study	Design Elements	Merits	Demerits	Maintenance Culture Improvement	Deductions and Design Solutions
Wennovation Hub	Aesthetic facades, efficient ventilation, well-planned interiors	- Aesthetically pleasing and interior spaces.	- Insufficient parking spaces. Excessive hardscape around (windows) in the building. - Minimal Inaccessibility for durable materials exterior spaces.	- Enhance ventilation through larger fenestration improve natural ventilation and airflow. - Prioritize connect interior to exterior spaces.	- Large windows or larger fenestration improve natural ventilation and airflow. - Prioritize connect interior to exterior spaces.

Case Study	Design Elements	Merits	Demerits	Maintenance Culture Improvement	Deductions and Design Solutions
	minimal columns.	obstruction of disabled views. - Durable building materials that aid maintenance.	of disabled individuals.	such as high-quality paint and glazed finishes, such as ceramic tiles to extend lifespan and reduce maintenance need for frequent needs.	High-quality durable paints and tiles, reduce the maintenance.
Zone Park	Tech Spacious parking, ventilated interiors, and	- well-conscious environment. Spacious	- Minimal use of natural ventilation. Excessive	- Use finishes that resist dirt to reduce maintenance (e.g., glazed tiles, and water damage. -	- Use of high-quality flooring and paints that resist dirt

Case Study	Design Elements	Merits	Demerits	Maintenance Culture Improvement	Deductions and Design Solutions
	landscaped area. - Well-ventilated interiors. Underutilized green spaces. Positive material choice impacting aesthetics and maintenance.	landscaped area. - Well-ventilated interiors. Underutilized green spaces. Positive material choice impacting aesthetics and maintenance.	landscaped area. - Well-ventilated interiors. Underutilized green spaces. Positive material choice impacting aesthetics and maintenance.	landscaped area. - Well-ventilated interiors. Underutilized green spaces. Positive material choice impacting aesthetics and maintenance.	landscaped area. - Well-ventilated interiors. Underutilized green spaces. Positive material choice impacting aesthetics and maintenance.
Technology HUB	Flexible spaces, - Aesthetic facades - Poor drainage - Vinyl tiles with - Vinyl tiles are glass-walled and interior spaces. on-site. - water and stain-durable and resist	Flexible spaces, - Aesthetic facades - Poor drainage - Vinyl tiles with - Vinyl tiles are glass-walled and interior spaces. on-site. - water and stain-durable and resist	Flexible spaces, - Aesthetic facades - Poor drainage - Vinyl tiles with - Vinyl tiles are glass-walled and interior spaces. on-site. - water and stain-durable and resist	Flexible spaces, - Aesthetic facades - Poor drainage - Vinyl tiles with - Vinyl tiles are glass-walled and interior spaces. on-site. - water and stain-durable and resist	Flexible spaces, - Aesthetic facades - Poor drainage - Vinyl tiles with - Vinyl tiles are glass-walled and interior spaces. on-site. - water and stain-durable and resist

Case Study	Design Elements	Merits	Demerits	Maintenance Culture Improvement	Deductions and Design Solutions
(International)	offices, co-working recreational spaces.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Well-planned interior spaces with natural minimal columns. - ventilation. - Well-landscaped and drained environment. - Ample circulation area. 	Insufficient	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - resistant properties - minimize the need for frequent cleaning. - Design overhangs to prevent moisture over building structure, and reducing costs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - water spillage, which enhances maintenance - Overhangs prevent external walls damage and protect help prevent cracks building structure, and mold growth, reducing maintenance costs.

This study focuses on improving the maintenance culture in public buildings, particularly in technology hubs. It includes case studies from different locations to observe the measures taken to enhance maintenance culture in these spaces. The objective of this study is to identify the significance of maintenance culture in technology hubs, explore the factors affecting it, and relate these findings to existing literature, as shown in the tables below.

Table 3.5.2: The Essence of Maintenance Culture (according to Campbell & Reyes-Picknell, 2006) in Public Buildings with Respect to Conducted Case Studies

Factors Affecting Maintenance Culture in SN Public Buildings	Preventive Measures	References (Case Studies/Plate)
<p>Poor Material Selection: Architects and developers often use new materials and methods</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> that have not been properly tested or researched. <p>As a result, many maintenance problems emerge in the future.</p>	<p>Building defects can be reduced by considering the availability of accurate and appropriate materials during the design stage.</p>	<p>3.4.1/all, 3.4.2/all, 3.4.3/all, 3.4.4/all</p>

**Factors Affecting Maintenance Culture in
SN Public Buildings**

2. **Poor Ventilation Design:** Natural ventilation in buildings is crucial for HVAC system design. Poor ventilation leads to ineffective removal of polluted indoor air, increasing maintenance costs.

3. **Ignoring Environmental Issues:** Buildings located in areas with adverse environmental conditions face challenges due to weather differences, which contribute to higher maintenance costs. Sustainability is a key consideration in building design.

Preventive Measures

To improve building maintenance, ventilation decisions made early in the design stage can have a significant impact on the building's performance.

Consider the environmental conditions of the site location when designing the building.

**References (Case
Studies/Plate)**

3.4.1/3.4.1.3,
3.4.4/3.4.4.3 (large windows for ventilation)

3.4.4 described the environmental condition that influenced the building design

Table 3.5.2: Factors Affecting Maintenance Culture in Buildings (according to Graham, 2009) with Respect to Conducted Case Studies

The tables above illustrate the factors that influence maintenance culture in public buildings and the preventive measures that can be implemented to improve it. These measures, informed by the case studies, focus on using appropriate materials, designing for natural ventilation, and considering environmental factors during the design phase to ensure the long-term sustainability and ease of maintenance for technology hubs.

This table provides a comprehensive view of how design elements and material selection can improve maintenance culture in technology hubs, based on case studies and their respective analysis. It also highlights the importance of integrating sustainable practices into the design process to reduce future maintenance needs.

The table provides an overview of three case studies on technology hub buildings, focusing on design elements, maintenance culture, merits, demerits, and potential improvements. **Wenovation Hub**, **Zone Tech Park**, and **Technology HUB** each demonstrate thoughtful design elements like well-planned interior spaces, ventilation, and material choices that promote sustainability and ease of maintenance. However, challenges such as insufficient parking, poor drainage, and underutilized green spaces are common in all three hubs. The case studies highlight the need for better maintenance culture through improved material selection, such as durable paints and tiles, and design considerations like larger windows for better ventilation and overhangs to prevent moisture-related damage.

The analysis emphasizes the importance of integrating sustainable practices in the design phase to reduce long-term maintenance costs. For example, using vinyl tiles in high-traffic areas and introducing overhangs to protect the building from rainwater damage can significantly extend the life of a building and reduce maintenance efforts. These improvements, along with better use of natural ventilation and the right choice of materials, will enhance the maintenance culture in technology hubs. Ultimately, the study suggests that well-designed, durable buildings with a focus on sustainability and proper maintenance planning are crucial for improving the overall quality and longevity of public buildings in Nigeria and globally.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study align with past research that emphasizes the critical role of maintenance culture in enhancing the longevity and functionality of public buildings. For example, Nahimah (2008) and Gurjit (2010) both highlighted how poor

maintenance practices contribute to the deterioration of public properties, a concern echoed in the case studies analyzed here, where buildings suffer from issues such as poor ventilation, inadequate parking, and underutilized spaces due to the lack of a strong maintenance culture. Similarly, the recommendation to use durable materials like high-quality paints and glazed ceramic tiles to reduce maintenance needs aligns with Kumar & Suresh (2008), who argued that the right materials can significantly extend the life of a facility. The focus on sustainable practices, such as the introduction of overhangs to prevent moisture-related damage, is also consistent with previous studies that underscore the importance of designing buildings with maintenance in mind to reduce long-term upkeep costs (Mobley, 2002).

However, the findings also present a more nuanced approach by integrating specific design solutions tailored to improve maintenance culture in technology hubs, which may not have been as explicitly addressed in previous research. While past studies like those by Swanson (2001) and Mobley (2004) discussed the importance of preventive maintenance, this study's emphasis on natural ventilation and space planning as part of the design process provides a more holistic view of how architectural choices directly impact maintenance culture. Furthermore, the case studies indicate that a shift towards considering maintenance during the early design phase, as recommended by Latham (1994) and Rounds (2018), could significantly improve building performance and reduce the deterioration rates seen in many Nigerian public buildings. This suggests that integrating maintenance considerations at the design stage is a critical factor in achieving sustainable infrastructure, which past studies may have underemphasized.

SUMMARY

This study focuses on improving the maintenance culture in public buildings, with a particular emphasis on technology hubs. By conducting case studies in various locations, the research aims to identify the significance of maintenance culture in these buildings and the factors that influence it. The study's objective is to examine the essence of maintenance culture, factors affecting it, and strategies for improving it,

drawing from existing literature and analyzing the case studies conducted. Through these case studies, the study also seeks to assess how thoughtful design, material selection, and sustainable practices can enhance the maintenance culture and overall quality of technology hub buildings.

One of the key factors identified in the research is poor material selection, which is often a result of using new materials that have not been adequately tested or researched. This leads to long-term maintenance problems. The study recommends considering the availability of appropriate materials during the design stage to reduce these issues. This finding aligns with previous research that emphasizes the importance of selecting durable, well-researched materials for the long-term sustainability of buildings. Case studies like Wennovation Hub, Zone Tech Park, and Technology HUB demonstrate how careful material choice can help mitigate maintenance challenges in the future.

Another significant factor affecting maintenance culture is poor ventilation design. Poor ventilation systems can lead to ineffective air circulation, which, in turn, increases maintenance costs due to the accumulation of pollutants. The study highlights the importance of incorporating adequate natural ventilation in the early design phase, such as through the use of large windows. This recommendation echoes prior research that suggests early design decisions, like improving ventilation, have a substantial impact on reducing long-term maintenance needs. Case studies further show that enhancing natural airflow improves both building performance and maintenance efficiency.

The study also explores how ignoring environmental conditions can negatively affect a building's maintenance culture. Environmental factors such as local climate and weather patterns are critical when designing buildings. Failure to consider these conditions can lead to increased maintenance costs due to issues like moisture damage. The research advocates for designing buildings with environmental considerations in mind to reduce the need for frequent repairs. This approach, supported by the case

studies, aligns with previous findings that emphasize the importance of sustainability in building design, with long-term maintenance being a key factor in the overall success of the building's operation. Through these analyses, the study provides actionable recommendations for improving maintenance culture in public buildings, especially technology hubs.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research highlights the critical role that maintenance culture plays in enhancing the quality and longevity of public buildings, particularly technology hubs. Through detailed case studies and empirical evidence, the study has demonstrated how thoughtful architectural design, material selection, and sustainable practices are fundamental in improving maintenance culture. The findings emphasize that the integration of these factors during the design phase can significantly reduce the long-term maintenance challenges faced by public buildings, ensuring they remain functional, sustainable, and efficient throughout their life cycle.

One of the key findings of this research is the impact of poor material selection on the maintenance culture of technology hubs. The use of inadequately tested or unsuitable materials leads to frequent maintenance issues, increasing operational costs and reducing the building's lifespan. To address this, the study recommends a more thoughtful approach to material choice, prioritizing durability and long-term performance. This aligns with existing literature that stresses the importance of using well-researched, high-quality materials to minimize maintenance needs. The case studies, such as Wenovation Hub and Zone Tech Park, support this recommendation by showing how careful material selection can significantly reduce the frequency and cost of repairs.

Another major finding is the importance of effective ventilation design in reducing maintenance costs. Poor ventilation systems, especially in buildings with inadequate natural airflow, can lead to an accumulation of pollutants, which accelerates

deterioration and increases maintenance efforts. The study suggests that larger windows and improved ventilation strategies be integrated into the design process to mitigate these issues. This recommendation is supported by the case studies, where buildings that prioritized natural ventilation showed better long-term performance and required less frequent maintenance. This finding further reinforces previous research that highlights the significant impact of design decisions on the overall maintenance needs of a building.

Finally, the study underscores the importance of considering environmental factors during the design process. Buildings located in regions with challenging weather conditions are prone to accelerated wear and tear if environmental considerations are overlooked. The research advocates for designing buildings that account for local climate conditions, thereby reducing the need for costly and frequent repairs. This is consistent with prior studies that stress the need for sustainability in building design. The case studies analyzed in this research show that incorporating these considerations into the design phase can help extend the life of a building and ensure that it remains functional and cost-effective for years to come. Overall, this research provides a comprehensive framework for improving maintenance culture in technology hubs, with practical recommendations that can be applied in the design and management of public buildings.

Recommendation 1: Improved Material Selection

One of the key findings of this study is the importance of selecting appropriate materials during the design phase to enhance the maintenance culture of public buildings. Poor material selection, particularly the use of untested or unsuitable materials, leads to increased maintenance challenges and reduced building longevity. Therefore, it is recommended that architects and developers prioritize the use of durable, well-researched, and tested materials in the construction of technology hubs.

Implementation Strategy: To implement this recommendation, it is essential for designers and developers to engage in thorough research and testing of materials before making any selections. Collaboration with material scientists and experts in building construction should be encouraged to ensure that materials chosen are suited to the local climate, building function, and long-term maintenance needs. Additionally, developers should invest in sourcing high-quality, low-maintenance materials that align with sustainability goals, such as energy-efficient windows and moisture-resistant wall finishes. Regular training and workshops for architects on emerging materials and their benefits should be organized to ensure that the latest, most durable materials are consistently used in new projects.

Recommendation 2: Incorporation of Natural Ventilation

The study highlights the critical role of effective ventilation in reducing maintenance costs and improving the overall functionality of public buildings. Poor ventilation systems contribute to the accumulation of pollutants and increased maintenance needs. It is recommended that the design of technology hubs should include provisions for natural ventilation, such as larger windows, open spaces, and cross-ventilation to enhance airflow and reduce dependency on mechanical ventilation.

Implementation Strategy: The implementation of this recommendation can be achieved by revising the building design phase to prioritize natural ventilation. This would involve adjusting the layout to ensure the strategic placement of windows, vents, and open spaces that facilitate airflow. Additionally, the design should account for climate and environmental conditions in the building's location to optimize ventilation. Designers should also incorporate features such as adjustable windows or vents that allow for user-controlled airflow. To ensure the success of these features, building management teams should conduct regular assessments of ventilation systems to confirm their effectiveness and make adjustments as needed, while ensuring that

natural ventilation is maintained alongside any mechanical systems. Incorporating these strategies from the outset will help in reducing long-term maintenance costs related to ventilation and improve indoor air quality.

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INFLUENCE OF SOCIOECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESIDENTS ON THE MAINTENANCE OF MASS HOUSING SCHEMES IN ILORIN METROPOLIS, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Socioeconomic background of residents is an important factor in housing provision for any population in the developed world. It is often believed that it influences certain behaviours. However in Nigeria, housing provision is usually done by the providers without the input of residents' background thereby leaving a gap on its influence on housing, most especially housing maintenance. This study therefore examines the effect of socioeconomic characteristics of residents on housing maintenance in mass housing schemes in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara state, Nigeria. The study is quantitative in nature and both primary and secondary data were utilized. It employed multistage sampling technique and a total of 1125 questionnaires constituting 27% of the sample frame were administered to household heads selected from public, private as well as public-private-partnership mass housing schemes. Data obtained were analysed with descriptive statistics, while pearson-product moment correlation (PPMC) was employed to analyse the relationship between socioeconomic characteristics of residents and housing maintenance. The study found out that the residents majorly aged 51 years and above, had HND/1st /postgraduate degree (81.0%) and are primarily government workers (37.0%). The highest monthly income (27.7%) was however above #121,000. There is a high (strong) positive correlation between socioeconomic characteristics of residents and maintenance of houses ($r=0.725$) implying socioeconomic characteristics are the determinants of housing maintenance in the area. The study therefore suggests among others that the socioeconomic characteristics of inhabitants of mass housing schemes should be factored both at the design and maintenance stage so as to ensure that the house will be sustainable in future.

Keywords: Influence, socioeconomic characteristics, residents, maintenance, mass housing schemes.

Introduction

There is a universal shortage of decent and well-maintained dwelling units in the less developed countries, Nigeria inclusive. Rapid population growth and urbanisation are creating escalating demands for added living spaces (Bajere, 1996; Amuda and Adewoye, 2020) and there is a wide gap between housing needs and efforts to increase the number and quality of available units.

According to Amuda and Adewoye (2020), there are several factors that cause the inadequacy of housing in the country among which is the high rate of unmaintained houses due to lack of maintenance culture. Houses are ageing, and in many cases, there is the need to repair, so as to prolong the life span. Research conducted by Cobbinah (2010) showed that over 80% of public residential buildings had maintenance problems and this is because, housing maintenance is not factored into housing production. Great emphasis is placed on the gap between housing demand and supply, but little attention is paid to the maintenance of existing housing stock (Obeng-Odoom and Amedzro 2011).

Mass housing schemes are repetitive housing solutions that have emerged as a complement of urban regeneration to cover the acute shortage of housing in cities. They are meant to solve housing problems; however, the country is far from achieving the goal (Ibimulua and Ibitoye, 2015; Adebimpe and Peters, 2018); the maintenance of mass housing schemes is often neglected and despite the pivotal roles of housing in socioeconomic development and the life of the people, majority of mass housing schemes are provided without the input of user.

In the developed world, socioeconomic characteristics of residents is an important factor in housing planning, most especially, mass housing schemes. According to Waziri et al (2014), socioeconomic characteristics of residents help policymakers and professionals in the building industry to consider the maintenance of mass housing schemes by carefully considering sustainable building materials for maintenance purpose. However, in Nigeria, there is a gap on the role of socioeconomic characteristics in mass housing schemes maintenance. Studies are either concentrated on mass housing scheme quality (Mbazor, 2018; Blome, 2010; Adeoye, 2018); delivery strategies (Cobbinah, 2010; Odunjo, Oladimeji and Okanlawon, 2015) and security measures (Foluke et.al, 2019) to mention a few. Thus, there is the need to find out the influence of socioeconomic characteristics of residents on housing maintenance in Nigeria. This study therefore examines the effects of socioeconomic residents on maintenance in mass housing schemes in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara state, Nigeria. This is with a view to improving the living conditions of the houses. In order to do this, a hypothesis was set for the study and this states that:

Ho- There is no relationship between socio-economic characteristics of residents and maintenance of mass housing schemes in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara state, Nigeria.

The Study Area

Ilorin is the capital of Kwara State in the middle belt of Nigeria. It is located on longitude 4° 27' 38.05" E, 4° 39' 15.11" E, and latitude 8° 23' 05.57"N, 8° 34' 09.39"N. It has a population of 908,490 as of 2011 making it the 13th largest city in Nigeria with a land area of 765 km sq. and density of 1,188/km square (Ogunjo, Oladimeji and Okanlawon, 2015). It lies in the savannah climatic region and has three local governments which are Ilorin East, Ilorin West and Ilorin South as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 : Map of Ilorin metropolis

Source: GIS Laboratory, Urban and Regional Planning Department, (LAUTECH 2021)

Figure 2: Map of Mass Housing Schemes in Ilorin metropolis
 Source: GIS Laboratory, Urban and Regional Planning Department, (LAUTECH 2021)

Ilorin is the largest city in Kwara state which is strategically located as the gateway between the north and southwestern Nigeria. This has led to the amalgamation of citizens from these regions who are predominantly of Islam (north) and Christianity (west) faiths respectively. This, therefore, contributes to making Ilorin, a confluence of cultures, populated by Yoruba, Hausa, Fulani, Nupe, Igbo, Baruba and other ethnic groups as well as foreign nationals with significant Christianity and Islamic faiths.

Recently, more people from western and eastern Nigeria previously resident in northern Nigeria migrated to Ilorin, because of insecurity challenges due to insurgencies. This coupled with the progress made by

the previous Governments of the State in their effort to bring investors to the state led to a relative increase in the economic activities of the city. There are a lot of mass housing schemes in Ilorin metropolis such as Harmony estate, Royal valley estate and Mandate estate etc as shown in Figure 2

Methodology

The population consists of all the mass housing schemes or the estates in Ilorin metropolis, while the unit of analysis is the house. All the houses constructed under the mass housing programme in the three local government areas of Ilorin, inclusive of Federal and State governments, Public-Private-Partnership (PPP) and the Organised Private Developers constituted the population for the study. Ilorin city is selected because it is the capital of Kwara State in which the State Government has given the highest priority in its mass housing programme.

However, the sample frame consists of houses completed (and occupied) by each of the stakeholders in the provision of housing. The total number of houses sold amounts to 4,166 which is the sample frame for the study. Multistage sampling technique was employed and the first stage was the stratification of the metropolis into local government areas. These are Ilorin West, Ilorin South and Ilorin East. The second stage involved the identification of mass housing schemes in each of the local government area. According to Kwara State Housing Corporation and

reconnaissance survey carried out, Federal government has two estates, which is the Low-cost estate and Ministerial housing estate. Kwara state government has eleven, PPP has four, while the Private sector has a total of eight estates.

In the third stage, information was collected on the details of the mass housing projects from the PPP and the private sector and in the last stage, the sample size was selected. To have a good representation of each of the housing delivery strategies, twenty-seven per cent (27%) of the houses were randomly sampled from the sample frame leading to a total of 1,125 samples for consideration. . Since there are different house types in the area, in order to ensure that the samples selected are representative of the population from which they are drawn, Equal Probability of Selection Method (EPSEM) was applied. The twenty-seven per cent sample from each of the housing delivery strategy was applied to the different house types in each estate or mass housing project. A sample was then randomly taken by drawing papers scripted with the number of houses contained in hats for each house type and in each housing delivery strategy. Thereafter, others were systematically selected at an interval of one after the other. Thus, the breakdown of the samples from each house type was 271, 923, 454, 146 and 4 houses in the 1,2,3,4,5-bedroom types of houses respectively. Data obtained were analysed using descriptive

statistics such as frequency counts and percentages, while Pearson-Product moment correlation was employed to analyse the relationship between socioeconomic characteristics of residents and housing maintenance.

Findings and Discussion

Socioeconomic Characteristics of Respondents

More than three-tenths (33.1%) of the respondents were 51 years and above. This was followed by 41-50 years (28.3%) and 31-40 years (20.2%). Respondents that were 21-30 years account for 16.4%, while, below 20 years constituted 2.0%. The implication of this is that majority of the respondents are adults and mature and it is expected that reliable information will be obtained from them regarding housing maintenance in the area.

However, the distribution of educational background of respondents as shown in Table 1 indicates that those with no formal education accounted for 4.9%, primary education were 0.3%, while 7.3%, 9.5% and 78.0% of respondents had modern/secondary education, Nursing certificate/NCE/OND and HND/1st degree/Postgraduate degree respectively. Thus, it can be inferred from the analysis that the education of the people in the mass housing schemes of Ilorin metropolis is largely high. This is not unexpected taking into consideration the fact that the

residents of mass housing schemes in Ilorin like any other city are mostly elite. This tends to suggest that the three mass housing delivery strategies provided housing mainly for the highly educated people, this is good as it will enable the respondents to position the existing situation of housing maintenance in their respective estates.

Furthermore, analysis shows that the respondents are majorly public sector (37.0%) workers. Those who work in the private sector accounted for 24.7%, while self-employed constituted 23.0%. Retirees/Pensioners were however 4.6% of the total respondents sampled, while the unemployed were 10.7%. The bulk (27.7%) of the respondents were collecting above N121,000 monthly, while the minimum salary of workers in the area was N31,000-N60,000 which is a little bit higher than the minimum wage in Nigeria. Thus, it is inferred that the majority of the residents are high-income and middle workers by Nigeria Standard.

Most households had a membership size of 4-6 persons (58.2%) followed closely by below 3 persons (24.1%) and 7-10 persons per house (12.4%) as shown in Table 1. The tendency towards large family size is indicated by the fact that a significant proportion (1.2%) of households had membership sizes of 11-13 persons and 14 persons and above (4.1%). Thus, there is the possible influence of family size on maintenance of the

house in which the size of family will dictate the amount to spend on housing maintenance as observed by Odunjo (2014)

Table 1: Socioeconomic Characteristics Background of Respondents

S/N	Variables	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)	
A	Age (years)	18 years and below	21	2.0
		19-30 years	171	16.4
		31-40 years	211	20.2
		41-50 years	295	28.3
		51 years and above	345	33.1
		Total	1043	100.0
B	Educational Background	HND/1 st degree/Postgraduate degree	814	78.0
		Nursing/NCE/OND	99	9.5
		Modern/ Secondary education	76	7.3
		Primary school	3	0.3
		No formal education	51	4.9
		Total	1043	100.0
		C	Employment Status	Public sector
Private sector	258			24.7
Self employed	240			23.0
Retiree/pensioners	48			4.6
Unemployed	111			10.7
Total	1043			100.0
D	Monthly Income	N30,000 and below	34	3.3
		N31,000-N60,000	181	17.4
		N61,000-N90,000	113	10.8
		N91,000-N120,000	116	11.1
		N121,000 and above	289	27.7
		Others	310	29.7
		Total	1043	100.0
E	Household Size	Below 3 persons	251	24.1
		4-6 persons	607	58.2
		7-10 persons	129	12.4
		11-14 persons	13	1.2
		14 persons and above	43	4.1
		Total	1043	100.0

Source: Authors' field survey (2021)

Housing Maintenance

The maintenance level of houses in the area was measured by the condition of houses at the time of fieldwork. Hence, housing condition was measured using five (5) variables which constitute the major elements of a building and are foundation, wall, roof, floor, and painting/tile which constitutes finishes. (Table 2)

Table 2: Housing Condition of Mass Housing Schemes in Ilorin

S/ N	Variabl es	Very good		Good		Fair		Poor		Very poor		Missing value		Total	
		Fre q. (N)	Per c. (%)	Fre q. (N)	Pe rc. (%)	Fr eq. (N)	Pe rc. (%)	Fr eq. (N)	Pe rc. (%)	Fr eq. (N)	Pe rc. (%)	Fr eq. (N)	Pe rc. (%)	Fre q. (N)	Pe rc. (%)
1.	Foundat ion	448	43.0	259	24.8	309	29.9	6	0.6	0	0	21	2.0	104	10
2.	Wall	273	26.2	314	30.1	379	36.3	57	5.5	0	0	20	1.9	104	10
3.	Roof	255	24.4	309	29.6	284	27.4	16	1.6	0	0	28	2.7	104	10
4.	Floor	224	21.5	441	42.3	303	29.3	43	4.1	0	0	32	3.1	104	10
5.	Painting /Tile	214	20.5	392	37.6	240	23.0	16	1.5	4	0.4	33	3.2	104	10

Source : Authors' field survey (2021)

Analysis shows that the bulk (43.0%) of foundation in the area were in very good condition, while there is none in very poor condition. This implies that foundations of houses in the area are relatively maintained and this could be due to the educational background of the

residents as well as the fact that they are mostly employed. However, walls in the area were majorly in fair condition (36.3%) which may be that only foundation is maintained at the expense of wall in order to avoid structural failure of the building. Furthermore, the dominant roof condition in the mass housing schemes was good (29.6%) as well as floor (42.3%), and painting /tile (37.6%).

Relationship between Socioeconomic Characteristics of Residents and Housing Maintenance

Variables were identified and used as socio-economic characteristics; they are age, educational level, employment status, monthly income and household size. Also, five (5) variables were identified for the maintenance of buildings. These variables are the maintenance of; foundation, wall, roof, floor, painting/tile. To make these variables suitable for Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis, they were summarized into one composite variable through the use of average computation. This was done and two (2) composite variables of socio-economic characteristics and maintenance level of houses were statistically obtained. They were thereby correlated and the result is contained in Table 3.

Table 3: Relationship between Socio-economic Characteristics of Residents and Maintenance of Houses

		Correlations	
		Socio-economic characteristics	Maintenance of houses
Socio-economic characteristics	Pearson Correlation	1	0.725**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	642	585
Maintenance of houses	Pearson Correlation	0.725**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	585	937

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Authors' Computation, (2021)

According to the table, with a correlation coefficient of 0.725, it is observed that there is a high (strong) positive correlation between the socio-economic characteristics of residents and the maintenance of houses. This implies that the socio-economic characteristics of residents influence the maintenance of houses considerably. Moreover, with a p-value of 0.000, it is also observed that there is a significant relationship between socio-economic characteristics of residents and maintenance of houses at $p < 0.05$ confidence level in the mass housing scheme in Ilorin metropolis.

Conclusion

The study has examined the relationship between socioeconomic characteristics and the maintenance of houses in mass housing schemes in

Ilorin metropolis. It shows that socioeconomic characteristics of residents are predictors of housing maintenance and have positive effects on the overall housing condition and level of maintenance.

Based on this conclusion, it is suggested that the socioeconomic characteristics of residents should be factored into housing planning both at the design and maintenance stage in order to provide houses that will be sustainable in future. Also, government and stakeholders involved in the provision of mass housing schemes should be using sustainable building materials that will be durable and easy to maintain. The stakeholders of the mass housing schemes should provide the necessary assistance to the residents in the maintenance of infrastructure in the mass housing schemes.

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